

Unravelling the Conundrum: Are Entrepreneurship Education and Personality Traits influential for Entrepreneurial Intentions in University Students

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Abstract

Purpose: The research objectives were to analyse the demographical factors that influence the entrepreneurial intentions of university students; To analyse the relationship between students Personality traits and the students' entrepreneurial intentions and to analyse how Entrepreneurship education, affects entrepreneurial intentions.

Design/methodology/approach: The data was collected through a questionnaire to evaluate variables that affect entrepreneurial intentions. The samples of the study included randomly selected, 254 undergraduate students, and the analysis was done using SPSS.

Findings: The study revealed that the Personality traits (Students' Attitudes) had an impact on the Entrepreneurial intention of the students. It is also revealed that the Perception of the students after Entrepreneurship education changes them and influenced their entrepreneurial intentions. Further, it is also confirmed that all the demographic factors did not influence the Entrepreneurial intention of the students but only the factors – Nationality and Residence influenced the Entrepreneurial intention of the students.

Research limitations/implications: It is recommended to offer a variety of technical/vocational courses to help entrepreneurs to overcome challenges, as well as a funding structure for students who pitch unique business ideas. Also, to have strong, leading, and social personality training, to make decisions, and to have crisis skills training in marketing, project development, business acceleration, customer service, etc. will also help the future interested entrepreneurs.

Social Implications : The formation of a community-wide culture of proper entrepreneurial practices, as well as its inclusion in the school curriculum, will help to build human capital towards embracing entrepreneurship in Oman. Educating future generations about entrepreneurship, developing its concept, encouraging pioneers, giving them all types of support, and creating the right investment climate will help them to become successful future entrepreneurs. Creating a national innovation system will open the door to a wider range of funding options as it provides a financial environment to students who propose unique ideas for new projects.

Originality / Value: The study was restricted to the selected variables such as Perception (after Entrepreneurship Education), Personality Traits (Students' Attitudes), and Entrepreneurial intention to Start a New Business. The study can be extended to all the other socio-economic factors. The study was dealt with students who had a basic knowledge of Entrepreneurship. Similar studies can be extended to all students who were not having Entrepreneurship Education etc.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, Perception after Entrepreneurship Education, Students' Attitudes, Personality Traits, Entrepreneurial Intention.

Introduction

The Sultanate of Oman is one of the largest oil producers in the Middle East. Oman's economy is dependent on the extraction and export of petroleum. Oman has been working for many years towards diversification

of its economy so that oil dependency could be reduced. The diversification effort is initiated to overcome the problem of unemployment in the country. At present, the graduates in Oman are undergoing the stress of unemployment as the unemployment rate keeps rising.

Oman's rate of unemployment rose from 1.8% (2019) to 5% (2020) and it was expected to reach 3.30 % by the end of 2021. In the long-term, the Oman unemployment rate is projected to trend around 3.20 % in 2022 and 3.00 % in 2023, according to the econometric models ([Trading Economics Global Macro Models Analysts, 2022](#)).

Figure.1 Oman Unemployment rate

At present, the Oman labor market is swarming and finding it difficult to accommodate more people. Although increased admittance to higher education in Oman to overcome unemployment issues through education, most of the jobs in the private sector are taken by the expatriate community ([Ali et al., 2017](#); [Magd & McCoy, 2014](#)). However, the Government of Oman is striving hard through tremendous efforts towards promoting entrepreneurship and encouraging small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in building ample job opportunities. There have been many supportive and motivated initiatives such as Riyada – SME Development Public Authority, Sharakah (Youth Projects Development Fund), CELL program, Intilaaqah, National Business Center (NBC), Zubair Small Enterprise Center (Zubair SEC), Aiesec Oman, Jisser Internship (Program) and Injaz ([Shah et al., 2020](#)).

Entrepreneurship plays an important role in the prosperity and stability of various countries mainly through reducing the problem of unemployment. Of late, the job possibilities in Oman are the result of the rise of SMEs ([Brinda Kalyani et al., 2015](#)). Oman is taking various measures to encourage entrepreneurship and young people to follow their entrepreneurial passions.

Special schemes are offered to upcoming entrepreneurs by the Riyada Public Authority for SMEs Growth. Further, SANAD and Al Raffd Funds have also been specifically established for Omani youth. The SANAD program is targeting the age group 18-40 years. This group range fresh graduates and job seekers who are all interested in starting new businesses or expanding existing businesses ([UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre, 2012](#)). Students are given special training programs in the field of entrepreneurship as a part of their curriculum. However, the impact of these shifts in student intentions on entrepreneurship is not known as it was never evaluated.

Though entrepreneurial analysis has spread considerably, there is a long list of factors that affect entrepreneurship. There is no full consensus that the need for performance and the locus of control will justify the intent of people to start businesses. Habit is one of the motivating forces for intentions and attitudes are the specific behavior people respond to in situations, and challenges. This is despite the gender differences arising among the motivating the moderating influences towards entrepreneurship, self-efficiency of entrepreneurs, and the desire for success ([Voda & Florea, 2019](#)). Independence and taking chances do not impact the entrepreneurial purpose of students coordinating their ventures directly.

Research Questions

1. What are the demographical factors that influence the entrepreneurial intention of the students?
2. What is the relationship between students Personality traits and the students' entrepreneurial intentions?
3. How does Entrepreneurship education affect entrepreneurial intentions?

Research Objectives

1. To analyse the demographical factors that influence the entrepreneurial intentions of students Universities
2. To analyse the relationship between students Personality traits and the students' entrepreneurial intentions
3. To analyse how Entrepreneurship education, affect entrepreneurial intentions

Problem statement

Though there are plenty of opportunities through Governmental and non-governmental schematic supports to motivate, guide, and initiate entrepreneurial ventures, there is a lag and hesitance among the Omani youth especially the students.

The proactive personality of students is affected by their business interests. The factors which inspire students to become entrepreneurs need to be analysed as the perception of the students and mind-set have to be known. It is also become necessary to know the socio-economic and demographic factors that stimulate the minds of the young students of Oman. In the recent past, studies were carried out focusing on the entrepreneurial achievement in Oman but not more on the entrepreneurial intention of the students. Research is needed to evaluate students' entrepreneurial intentions and the variables that influence their decisions.

Review of Literature

Entrepreneurial features had a major influence on business students towards launching new businesses – Locus of the students' check and the level of imagination were influencing more whereas the influence of self-confidence was least ([Al-Nashmi & Almamary, 2017](#)).

Perception of the students after Entrepreneurship Education

In Oman, training centres and colleges of technology promote the culture of entrepreneurship through entrepreneurship education ([Al-Abri et al., 2018](#)). Education is strongly associated with the desire to start a new business as education plays an important role in the intention of building a new business ([Hunjra et al., 2011](#); [Packham et al., 2010](#)). Entrepreneurship education is central to student entrepreneurship ([Saeed et al., 2015](#)). Entrepreneurship education inspires students to choose entrepreneurship as a career path and provides them with the essential skills ([Fatoki & Oni, 2014](#)). [Jaafar and Aziz \(2008\)](#) found that the effect of entrepreneurship courses on people's willingness to start their own businesses at any stage in their careers is strong. [Cheng et al. \(2009\)](#) confirmed that education in entrepreneurship inspires students to become entrepreneurs and quality the students to be entrepreneurs. Higher education, and business angels influence graduates' attitudes ([Ibrahim et al., 2017](#)). [Brinda Kalyani et al. \(2015\)](#) found that business education is directly linked to business goals. According to [Segumpan and Zahari \(2012\)](#), Omani university students in business institutions have optimistic attitudes toward entrepreneurship. [Jena \(2020\)](#) & [Lorz and Volery \(2011\)](#) confirmed that entrepreneurship education had an impact on entrepreneurial intention. [Karimi et al. \(2016\)](#) found that the impacts elective entrepreneurship education had more impact than the compulsory program on students' entrepreneurial intention. Entrepreneurship education programs influence the students' attitudes and entrepreneurial intentions ([Fayolle & Gailly, 2015](#)).

However, there was a difference of opinion such as the effects of entrepreneurial education does not foster entrepreneurship intention ([Wegner et al., 2019](#)) and Entrepreneurship education is not said to benefit all as female students were seemed to have less intensity of entrepreneurial intention ([Westhead & Solesvik, 2016](#)).

Personality Traits (Students' Attitudes)

Need for achievement and risk tolerance are a few of the personality traits which impact entrepreneurial intention ([Karabulut, 2016](#)). The motivation to act is also the personal will to act according to one's choices, representing the ability to deliberate ([Fayolle & Degeorge, 2006](#)). Creativity mediates the effect of entrepreneurs' self-efficacy and entrepreneurship ([Mushtaq & Khan, 2012](#)). Behavioral motives are directives to be followed in some way by individuals. It is deliberate to recognize openings, which is why the analysis of motives is crucial ([Duval-Couetil & Long, 2014](#)). Students can create a more favorable attitude towards business by promoting business knowledge and emphasizing the necessity of entrepreneurship ([Zhang et al., 2014](#)). [Khan and Almoharby \(2007\)](#) confirmed that entrepreneurial activities are important for the future development and expansion of GCC economies as the entrepreneurial strategies can also help students to have a positive attitude and create a goal. [Kristiansen and Indarti \(2004\)](#) claimed that the

perceptions of self-efficacy impacted the entrepreneurial intention while age, gender, and educational background had no impact. Openness and emotion had a direct impact on the intention of the students ([Kristiansen & Indarti, 2004](#)).

Many students in Oman have entrepreneurial characteristics and talents, and there is a high level of interest in entrepreneurial activities ([Panikar & Washington, 2011](#)). Students are improvising their creative to explore their entrepreneurial potentials through education ([Al Jahwari et al., 2020](#)). Individual motivations form the basis for the entrepreneurial intention of the students ([Saeed et al., 2015](#)). [Nasip et al. \(2017\)](#) confirmed that innovativeness, self-confidence, propensity to take the risk, need for achievement, and tolerance for ambiguity were the factors influencing students' entrepreneurial intention. [Shah et al. \(2020\)](#) claimed that attitude toward entrepreneurship and self-efficacy were the crucial factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions.

Entrepreneurial Intention

Entrepreneurship is the best clairvoyant of the entrepreneurial intention ([Krueger Jr et al., 2000](#)). [Tufa \(2021\)](#) claimed that the influence of the intention to start a new business had a direct impact on self-employment. [Ibrahim et al. \(2017\)](#) found that Omani students have strong attitude toward entrepreneurship but a low willingness to start new set-ups. [Mares et al. \(2016\)](#) & [Sahinidis et al. \(2014\)](#) have identified a beneficial connection between entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intentions. [Al Jahwari et al. \(2020\)](#) revealed that the intention to become an entrepreneur is mostly triggered by their graduate potentials, and the education. [Zvarikova and Kacerauskas \(2017\)](#) claimed that entrepreneurial intention of the students was based on an entrepreneur in the family, the existence of a business environment, suitable credit facilities, and educational background. It is better to know the perception and the entrepreneurial intention of the students so that their contribution can be helpful to the development of the country ([Rasli et al., 2013](#); [Turker & Selcuk, 2009](#)). One of the primary entrepreneurial intentions was to obtain a social status ([Khan et al., 2021](#)). However, the entrepreneurial intention might not be related to the success or independence ([Saeed et al., 2015](#)). Socio-demographic and other environmental factors highly impact the entrepreneurial intention of students ([Khuong & An, 2016](#); [Liñán et al., 2011](#); [Wang & Wong, 2004](#)). [Tierney et al. \(2011\)](#) claimed that the university students seem to have more potential towards beginning small enterprise undertakings in the future than graduate students.

[Vuong et al. \(2020\)](#) claimed that entrepreneurship intention is based on entrepreneurial education, personal characteristics, feasibility, and finance.

From the above literature review, it was confirmed that the variables considered in the study include Entrepreneurship education, Personality traits of the students (Attitudes) and socio-demographic variables as the independent variables, and Entrepreneurial intention as the dependent variable.

Further, the following hypotheses were derived:

Research Hypotheses

The subsequent hypotheses are established:

1. Gender, Specialization, Age, Nationality, and Residence have an impact on students' entrepreneurial intentions.
2. Personality traits have an impact on the students' entrepreneurial intentions.
3. Entrepreneurship education influences entrepreneurial intentions.

Research Methodology

A survey was used for the collection of data. The population of this paper consisted of undergraduate students at the university during the fall semester of 2021. The sample of this study included 254 students randomly drawn from the population. The data was collected through a questionnaire intended to evaluate variables that affect entrepreneurial intentions. The reliability analysis was conducted using SPSS to determine the validity of the instrument which had a Cronbach alpha value of 0.928.

Table 1 Demographic Details

	Category	Frequency	%
Nationality	Non-Omani	18	7.1
	Omani	236	92.9
Gender	Female	179	70.5
	Male	75	29.5
Marital Status	Divorced	2	0.8
	Engaged	7	2.8
	Married	54	21.3
	Single	191	75.2
Age	20-29	216	85.0
	30-39	32	12.6
	40-49	4	1.6
	50 years & above	2	.8
Specialisation	Business Management	133	52.4
	Engineering	27	10.6
	English Language	26	10.2
	IT	47	18.5
	Law	15	5.9
	Literature	6	2.4
Educational Qualification	Diploma	66	26.0
	Graduate	71	28.0
	High school	20	7.9
	No education (Illiterate)	6	2.4
	Post-graduate	6	2.4
	Undergraduate	85	33.5
Family Owning business	No	129	50.8
	yes	125	49.2
Family Income	< 500 OR	104	40.9
	500-1000 OR	102	40.2
	> 1000 OR	48	18.9
Family Members	1-4	39	15.4
	5-7	92	36.2
	Over 7	123	48.4
Residence	Bahla	3	1.2
	Barka	8	3.1
	Dhank	3	1.2
	Duqm	1	.4
	Ibra	3	1.2
	Ibri	29	11.4
	Izki	4	1.6
	Liwa	7	2.8
	Mahdah	1	.4
	Nakhhal	3	1.2
	Nizwa	8	3.1
	Rustaq	7	2.8
	Saham	32	12.6
	Salala	2	.8
	Shinas	26	10.2
	Sohar	44	17.3
	Suwayq	28	11.0
	Yanqul	17	6.7
	Others	28	11.0
Governorate	Ad-Dachiliyah	12	4.7
	Al-Buraimi	6	2.4
	Al-Dahirah	48	18.9

	Al-Wusta	1	.4
	Dhofar	1	.4
	Musandam	5	2.0
	Muscat	10	3.9
	North Al-Batinah	88	34.6
	North Al-Sharqiyah	5	2.0
	South Al-Batinah	69	27.2
	South Al-Sharqiyah	9	3.5
Working Status	Student	153	60.2
	Working	50	19.7
	Not Working	51	20.0

Perception

Table 2 Perception after Entrepreneurship Education

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S value	Chi-square	p-value
Have self –confidence to lead a new business	31 12.2%	76 29.9%	40 15.7%	68 26.8%	39 15.4%	.209	194.520	.000
I have the opportunity to learn new things	34 13.4%	62 24.4%	56 22%	72 28.3%	30 11.8%	.189		
Starting new business, I can achieve self-realization	43 16.9%	57 22.4%	55 21.7%	64 25.2%	35 13.8%	.176		
To start a new business, I should learn about entrepreneurship	47 18.5%	63 24.8%	46 18.1%	65 25.6%	33 13%	.184		
Starting a new business, I will use my skills and talents	44 17.3%	64 25.2%	44 17.3%	71 28%	31 12.2%	.196		
I have a high energy level to work hard	36 14.2%	72 28.3%	52 20.5%	60 23.6%	34 13.4%	.194		
I have a clear understanding of a business	32 12.6%	64 25.2%	59 23.2%	66 26%	33 13%	.176		
I bear responsibility for my own success and failures	31 12.2%	79 31.1%	50 19.7%	68 26.8%	26 10.2%	.208		
Starting a new business, I will control of my future	40 15.7%	68 26.8%	49 19.3%	67 26.4%	30 11.8%	.189		
I can excel with my full potentials	35 13.8%	78 30.7%	38 15%	77 30.3%	26 10.2%	.215		

Null Hypothesis: There is no relationship between the Perception after entrepreneurship education and the choices of the respondents.

Table 2 indicates that the p-value <0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis gets rejected. i.e. there is a significant relationship between the Perception after entrepreneurship education and the choice of respondents. Comparing the K-S values obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it is observed that ‘I can excel with my full potentials’ (0.215) ranked first followed by ‘Have self –confidence to lead a new business’ (0.209) and ‘I bear responsibility for my own success and failures’ (0.208) ranked third.

Entrepreneurial intention

Table 3 Entrepreneurial Intention to Start a New Business

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S Value	Chi-square	p-Value
Expecting more financial benefits by starting my own business	40 15.7%	70 27.6%	51 20.1%	68 26.8%	25 9.8%	.191	272.039	.000
Expecting more benefits through a new start-up	25 9.8%	78 30.7%	63 24.8%	69 27.2%	19 7.5%	.198		
To achieve my self-realized goals, I would like to start a new business	38 15%	66 26%	54 21.3%	72 28.3%	24 9.4%	.189		
Starting a new business, I will contribute to the growth and development of Oman	39 15.4%	66 26%	57 22.4%	72 28.3%	20 7.9%	.196		
I will get social status through starting a business	41 16.1%	68 26.8%	51 20.1%	72 28.3%	22 8.7%	.190		
To have a better future, I would like to start a new business	34 13.4%	64 25.2%	74 29.1%	56 22%	26 10.2%	.163		
It is a good idea to be self-employed	34 13.4%	70 27.6%	59 23.2%	65 25.6%	26 10.2%	.184		
Highly motivated by the success of other entrepreneurs	40 15.7%	77 30.3%	53 20.9%	61 24%	23 9.1%	.204		
I am willing to take up the risk	38 15%	66 26%	67 26.4%	59 23.2%	24 9.4%	.172		
Starting your own business is better than having a job	43 16.9%	65 25.6%	58 22.8%	65 25.6%	23 9.1%	.177		

Null Hypothesis: There is no relationship between the Entrepreneurial intention to Start a New Business and the choice of the respondents.

Table 3 indicates that the p-value <0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis gets rejected. i.e. there is a significant relationship between the Entrepreneurial intention to start a New Business and the choice of respondents. Comparing the K-S values obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it is observed that ‘Highly motivated to start a business observing the success of other entrepreneurs’ (0.204) ranked first followed by ‘Expecting more benefits through a new start-up’ (0.198) ranked and ‘Starting a new business, I will contribute to the growth and development of Oman’ (0.196) ranks third.

Attitudes

Table 4 Students’ Attitudes/Personality Traits towards Entrepreneurship

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S Value	Chi-square	p-Value
I can swiftly make my own decisions	44 17.3%	72 28.3%	54 21.3%	66 26%	18 7.1%	.194	210.370	.000
I am willing to undertake risks	36 14.2%	76 29.9%	58 22.8%	65 25.6%	19 7.5%	.189		
I am keen to start my own business	34 13.4%	70 27.6%	62 24.4%	61 24%	27 10.6%	.183		

I would like to take full responsibility for the success and failures of my business	44 17.3%	64 25.2%	54 21.3%	67 26.4%	25 9.8%	.179		
Having resources and I can start my own business	49 19.3%	63 24.8%	52 20.5%	72 28.3%	18 7.1%	.189		
I know markets, industries, and business regulations to start a new business	39 15.4%	66 26%	66 26%	67 26.4%	16 6.3%	.173		
I am ready to face the difficulties that may arise during a new venture	48 18.9%	64 25.2%	59 23.2%	69 27.2%	14 5.5%	.177		
Having strong desire to achieve positive results with utmost effort & dedication	30 11.8%	77 30.3%	65 25.6%	63 24.8%	19 7.5%	.195		
I have a good network of friends, professional, and business acquaintances	42 16.5%	61 24%	61 24%	65 25.6%	25 9.8%	.170		

Null Hypothesis: There is no relationship between the Students’ Attitudes Personality Traits towards Entrepreneurship and the choice of the respondents.

Table 4 indicates that the p-value <0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis gets rejected. i.e. there is a significant relationship between the Students’ Attitudes/Personality traits towards entrepreneurship and the choice of respondents. Comparing the K-S values obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it is observed that ‘Having strong desire to achieve positive results with utmost effort & dedication’ (0.195) ranked first, followed by ‘I can swiftly make my own decisions’ (0.194), and ‘I am willing to undertake risks’ (0.189) and ‘Having resources and I can start my own business (0.189).

Regression Analysis

Table 5 (a), (b), (c) and (d) Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Governorate, Gender, Educational Qualification, Nationality (N), Marital Status, Perception after Entrepreneurship Education (P), Specialization, Members In The Family, Residence (R), Working Status, Age, Students’ Attitudes/Personality Traits towards Entrepreneurship (T)	...	Enter

^aDependent Variable: Entrepreneurial intention to start a new business

^bAll requested variables entered

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.909 ^a	.827	.818	4.37640

^aPredictors: (Constant), Governorate, Gender, Educational qualification, Nationality (N), Marital status, Perception after entrepreneurship education (P), Specialization, Members in the family, Residence (R), Working status, Age, Personality Traits (Students' Attitudes) towards entrepreneurship (P)

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	22066.368	12	1838.86	96.010	.000 ^b
Residual	4615.841	241	4		
Total	26682.209	253	19.153		

^aDependent Variable: Entrepreneurial intention to start a new business

^bPredictors: (Constant), Governorate, Gender, Educational qualification, Nationality (N), Marital status, Perception after entrepreneurship education, Specialization, Members in the family, Residence (R), Working status, Age, Personality Traits (Students' attitudes) towards entrepreneurship (T)

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.602	3.815		1.469	.143
P	.413	.042	.442	9.840	.000
T	.561	.052	.498	10.762	.000
Nationality	-2.656	1.193	-.066	-2.226	.027
Gender	-.833	.674	-.037	-1.236	.218
Marital Status	.223	.558	5.602	.399	.690
Age	.525	.711	.024	.739	.461
Specialization	-.379	.198	-.055	-1.909	.057
Educational Qualification	-.246	.135	-.050	-1.818	.070
Working Status	.127	.243	.016	.524	.601
Members in The Family	.285	.407	.020	.701	.484
Residence	.163	.063	.078	2.603	.010
Governorate	-.005	.105	-.001	-.046	.964

^aDependent Variable: Entrepreneurial intention to start a new business

The p-values for Gender, Marital status, Age, Specialization, Educational qualification, Working status, Members in the family and Governorate are > 0.05.

Therefore, eliminating those variables, the regression analysis is carried out again, and thus obtained results are as follows:

Table 6 (a), (b), (c) and (d) Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Residence (R), Students' Attitudes/Personality Traits towards Entrepreneurship (T), Nationality (N), Perception after entrepreneurship education (P)	...	Enter

^aDependent Variable: Entrepreneurial intention to Start a New Business

^bAll requested variables entered

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.906 ^a	.820	.818	4.38653

^aPredictors: (Constant), Residence (R), Students' Attitudes/Personality Traits towards entrepreneurship (T), Nationality (N), Perception after entrepreneurship education (P)

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	21891.029	4	5472.757		
Residual	4791.180	249	19.242	284.422	.000 ^b
Total	26682.209	253			

^aDependent Variable: Entrepreneurial intention to Start a New Business

^aPredictors: (Constant), Residence (R), Personality Traits (Students' Attitudes) towards Entrepreneurship (T), Nationality (N), Perception after Entrepreneurship Education (P)

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.725	2.604		1.814	.071
P	.413	.041	.442	10.006	.000
T	.554	.051	.492	10.793	.000
N	-2.476	1.145	-.062	-2.163	.031
R	.192	.057	.092	3.366	.001

^aDependent Variable: Entrepreneurial intention to start a new business

Since all the p-values < 0.05, thus, the linear regression line is obtained as follows:

$$EI = 4.725 + 0.413 P + .0554 T + (-2.476) N + 0.192 R$$

where EI is Entrepreneurial intention to start a new business

P is Perception after Entrepreneurship education

T is Personality traits (Students' Attitudes)

N is Nationality

R is Residence

There is an association between (i) Perception after Entrepreneurship education, (ii) Personality traits (Students' Attitudes), (iii) Nationality, and (iv) Residence and Entrepreneurial intention to start a new business.

From the above coefficients, it can be seen that the Perception after Entrepreneurship education and Personality traits (Students' Attitudes) have more impact on the Entrepreneurial intention of the students to start a new business whereas the demographic factors Nationality and Residence have lesser impact whereas the other demographic factors - Gender, Educational qualification, Marital status, Specialization, Members in the family, Working status, Age, and Governorate did not influence the Entrepreneurial intention of the students to start a new business.

Discussion

Most of the respondents (50.8%) reported that their family-owned businesses and the majority of the respondents were belonging to lower-income groups as their income level was less than 500 OMR.

Amongst the Perception factors, 'I can excel with my full potentials' (0.215) was ranked first followed by 'Have self-confidence to lead a new business' (0.209) and 'I bear responsibility for my own success and failures' (0.208) ranked third.

Amongst the Entrepreneurial intention factors, 'Highly motivated to start a business observing the success of other entrepreneurs' (0.204) was ranked first followed by 'Expecting more benefits through a new start-up' (0.198) ranked and 'Starting a new business, I will contribute to the growth and development of Oman' (0.196) ranks third.

Amongst the Personality Traits factors, 'Having strong desire to achieve positive results with utmost effort & dedication' (0.195) ranked first, followed by 'I can swiftly make my own decisions' (0.194), and 'I am willing to undertake risks' (0.189) and 'Having resources and I can start my own business' (0.189).

It is observed that there is an association between (i) Perception after Entrepreneurship education, (ii) Personality traits (Students' Attitudes), (iii) Nationality, (iv) Residence, and Entrepreneurial intention to start a new business. The Perception after Entrepreneurship education and Personality traits (Students' Attitudes) have more impact on the intention of the students to start a business (Entrepreneurial intention). But the demographic factors - Gender, Educational Qualification, Nationality, Marital Status, Specialization, Members in The Family, Residence, Working Status, Age, and Governorate – all did not influence the Entrepreneurial intention to Start a New Business.

In other words, Personality traits (Students' Attitudes) have an impact on the Entrepreneurial intention of the students i.e. Hypothesis No.2 is proved positively and Entrepreneurship education has an influence on entrepreneurial intentions i.e. Hypothesis No.3 is proved positively. Also, all the demographic factors did not influence the Entrepreneurial intention of the students. Only Nationality and Residence influenced the Entrepreneurial intention of the students i.e. Hypothesis No.1 is proved partially.

Conclusion

The current study is an initial attempt to investigate Omani youth's entrepreneurial attitudes and ambitions, with a focus on university and college students, to focus more explicitly on students' perspectives. Students' perceptions of business prospects, barriers, motives, personal entrepreneurial exposure, expected family support, and culture were found to impact their attitudes (personality traits) and their goals (intention to start new businesses).

It was confirmed that the Personality traits (Students' Attitudes) have an impact on the Entrepreneurial intention of the students. Further, the Perception of the students after Entrepreneurship education changes them and influences their entrepreneurial intentions. Further, it is also confirmed that all the demographic factors did not influence the Entrepreneurial intention of the students but only the factors – Nationality and Residence influenced the Entrepreneurial intention of the students.

Entrepreneurship among young people can enhance economic development. Oman needs innovation and research development in the domain of entrepreneurship. Researchers and policymakers will use the findings to assess the success of entrepreneurship education.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were suggested:

1. The formation of a community-wide culture of proper entrepreneurial practices, as well as its inclusion in the school curriculum, will help to mold human capital to embrace entrepreneurship in Oman.
2. Educating future generations about entrepreneurship, developing its concept, embracing and encouraging pioneers, giving them all types of support, and creating the right investment climate will help them to become successful future entrepreneurs.
3. It is also important to offer a variety of technical/vocational courses to help entrepreneurs to overcome challenges, as well as a funding structure for students who pitch unique business ideas.
4. To have strong, leading, and social personality training, to make decisions, and to have crisis skills training in marketing, project development, business acceleration, customer service, etc. will also help them.

5. Creating a national innovation system that aids in revenue diversification is crucial. For entrepreneurs with new ideas, this opens the door to a wider range of funding options as it provides a financial environment to students who propose unique ideas for new projects.

Based on the above findings and recommendations a conceptual model is developed named Entrepreneurial Intention Model (E.I. Model) which is shown in Figure.2 as follows:

Figure.2 Entrepreneurial Intention Model

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